

The Enciphered Signature of Nicholas of Cusa in the Tarocchi del Mantegna: Cryptanalysis Using 15th-Century Techniques and Deterministic Proof

Author: Anuar Zacarías

Date: October 25, 2025

Date and title of preliminary deposit: May 14, 2025, *Summary and Table of Contents of the Unpublished Work "Tarocchi de Figura Mundi. The Globe Game of Nicholas of Cusa"*.

PRELIMINARY NOTE

The present document updates and substantially expands the preliminary Zenodo deposit of May 14, 2025, which established the initial hypotheses of this research. This new version incorporates: (a) terminological corrections and conceptual precision; (b) explicit cryptanalysis, based on documented fifteenth-century techniques, to identify the enciphered signature of Nicholas of Cusa in four allegories of the set; (c) statistical validation through Monte Carlo simulations and deterministic proof; and (d) synthesis of iconographic and biographical analysis. I have also modified the subtitle of the unpublished work, which is now titled *Tarocchi de Figura Mundi. Deciphering the Lost Libellus of Nicholas of Cusa*, planned in three volumes. These findings were presented at the Geheimschriftenzoom (University of Wuppertal, October 24, 2025), an international virtual conference on historical cryptography, under the title "An Enciphered Philosophical System and the Possible Signature of Nicholas of Cusa in the Tarocchi of Mantegna, Series E, 15th Century: Cryptanalysis and Evidence."

In the preliminary deposit I established both an intersemiotic and chronological relationship between the "Tarocchi del Mantegna" (ca. 1460-1465) and the title of a lost work by the Cusan: the *Libellus De figura mundi* ("little book on the figure of the world"), dated 1462 and sometimes linked to his treatise *De ludo globi* (1463, "The Globe Game"). On that occasion I suggested that the *De figura mundi* "could be a brief volume containing the fifty allegories" of the Tarocchi. However, after verifying that this set of 50 engravings constitutes an enciphered philosophical system, I now interpret it precisely as a *libellus* that transmits various hidden messages, decipherable only through the appropriate combination of its allegories and names. Some copies of this set were even bound as a book. This hypothesis, which identifies the so-called Tarocchi del Mantegna with Cusa's lost work, has led me to rename it as *Tarocchi de Figura Mundi*.

ABSTRACT

This document presents substantial evidence of an enciphered signature attributable to Nicholas of Cusa in the set of fifty fifteenth-century allegories known as “Tarocchi del Mantegna” (Italian Series E). Through cryptographic techniques documented in Roger Bacon's *Epistola de secretis operibus artis et naturae et de nullitate magiae* (ca. 1267) and Leon Battista Alberti's treatise *De componendis cifris* (1467), I have identified the name “NICOLAC” inscribed in four allegories linked to the cosmic principle of Mercury. The probability of this occurring by chance is 0.000433% (1 in 230,300 combinations), a result confirmed through 500,000 Monte Carlo simulations and a deterministic proof.

This finding is part of an innovative interdisciplinary study that interweaves philosophy, iconology, historical cryptanalysis, philology, and history, necessary to unravel truths that have remained veiled for nearly six centuries.

For the first time, this set of allegories is presented in my work as an enciphered philosophical system that reflects a dynamic image of the Cosmos (*figura mundi*), coherent with Cusan thought. Although it does not constitute explicit and direct documentary proof, it constitutes a significant indication of Cusa's intellectual authorship, or, to a lesser degree, of his closest circle.

The present document details only the finding of the enciphered signature NICOLAC. The complete research includes additional findings not revealed here:

- *Structural correspondence*: The five series of the Tarocchi conform precisely to the Cusan cosmological model, which also articulates five levels of the cosmos and attributes ontological and symbolic relevance to the number ten at each of these levels.
- *System of ruptures-differentiations*: Five systematic visual and structural discontinuities that reflect categorial ruptures in the representation of the Cosmos.
- *Circularity and transversality*: Allegorical concordances and numerical sequences that reveal a circularity among groups of allegories, as well as ruptures of the medieval-hierarchical cosmos through transversal connections, not only vertical ones.
- *Anagrammatic network*: More than fifteen philosophical anagrams identified in the set.
- *Enciphered messages*: Philosophical-theological words and aphorisms encoded in the allegories.
- *Cusan diagrams*: Correspondences between Cusa's visual diagrams and the structure of the Tarocchi.
- *Intertextuality*: Abundant correspondences between the structure and allegories of the Tarocchi with passages from Cusan works.

These findings will be published in the first months of 2026 in volume 1 of *Tarocchi de Figura Mundi. Deciphering the Lost Libellus of Nicholas of Cusa*, a three-volume study. The first volume contains 11 chapters and more than 300 pages. This deposit establishes precedence of discovery dated from May 14, 2025, protecting the intellectual authorship of the research.

1. CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH

Art historians have proposed various artists and engravers as possible executors of the so-called Tarocchi del Mantegna, including Andrea Mantegna, Baccio Baldini, Parrasio Micheli, Lazzaro Bastiani, and Francesco Squarcione, a question that must be elucidated by specialists in medieval and Renaissance art. In contrast, this study focuses on the intellectual authorship of the work, not on its material execution.

Regarding the intellectual authorship of the design and allegorical program of the Tarocchi, various names have been proposed: Ludovico Lazzarelli, Basilio Bessarion, Nicholas of Cusa, Pope Pius II, and I also consider in my analysis Leon Battista Alberti and Federico da Montefeltro. However, the only figure whose thought fully and verifiably conforms to the combinatorics and structure identified in these 50 allegories is the Cusan. His philosophy fulfills all the philosophical, cryptographic, chronological, and linguistic elements detected in this research on the Tarocchi.

For the first time, the Tarocchi are presented here as an enciphered philosophical system that precisely combines two languages—learned Latin and fifteenth-century Venetian—that enable the formation of anagrams, common phonetic roots, letter permutations, and combinatorics. These cryptographic operations are identified through a series of anomalies: strikethroughs, inverted or omitted letters, insertions of words within others, errors in numbering or in the series letter, symbolic abbreviations, and atypical Roman numeration, among other keys. Some of these techniques were documented in the works of Roger Bacon and Leon Battista Alberti, authors known to Cusa.

Similarly, the Tarocchi reflect an innovative cosmic structure and image that breaks with the medieval hierarchical model and anticipates the dynamic Cusan cosmos. Their linguistic fabric, which precisely and in a controlled manner combines allegorical names in learned Latin and in fifteenth-century Venetian dialect, lacks documented precedents in allegorical works of this period and appears to reflect Cusan *concordantia*. This philological phenomenon is not only stylistically unusual but also reveals a deliberate combinatorial intention that facilitates the formation of significant anagrams and connections that I have termed crypto-onomastic. Thus, I have identified various enciphered messages consistent with Cusan philosophy and mystical theology.

This triple articulation—innovative cosmology, cryptography, and philology—requires the simultaneous mastery of three specialized fields. For example, the idea of an infinite, dynamic cosmos without a fixed center is one of the particularities of Cusan cosmology, recognized by Bruno and by the subsequent philosophical tradition. Therefore, other authors of the same period—or even admirers and imitators of the Cusan—can be ruled out with reasonable certainty, since it is improbable that such conceptions and abilities would coincide in them. The combinatorial genius, the sophistication of the system, and the philosophical-cryptographic coherence of the Tarocchi cannot easily be explained as the work of a simple imitator, admirer, or disciple of the cardinal. Conceiving an entire game as a memory machine, cosmos in miniature, and cryptogram requires an original mind of Nicholas of Cusa's intellectual stature. Nevertheless, the hypothesis of a Cusan imitator cannot be completely ruled out until a document appears that explicitly relates Cusa to these engravings.

The Tarocchi were conceived as a dynamic image of the Cosmos that functions as philosophical-combinatorial cryptography: their allegories, anagrams, letters, and symbols construct an enigmatic language destined to veil and reveal mystical, metaphysical, and sapiential knowledge. In *De ludo globi* (1463) Cusa states: “It has been written that God is hidden 'from the eyes of all' the wise and that all the invisible is concealed in the visible. The visible is manifest to the eyes and the invisible is distant from the eyes.”¹ The Tarocchi would be precisely a manifestation of this principle.

They constitute a philosophical framework linked to *scientia aenigmatica* and to the Cusan conception of knowledge as a combinatorial product of signs and symbols that approximate truth, developed in works such as the *Compendium* and *De docta ignorantia*. Thus, the Tarocchi are inscribed in the Hermetic-philosophical tradition of the Renaissance, in continuity with the Lullian *ars combinatoria*, and anticipate later ciphering techniques developed by Alberti, Abbot Trithemius, and Giordano Bruno.

In this research, the Tarocchi are presented as an enciphered system that employs images, letters, numbers, and symbols, whose key lies in the combinatorial structure rather than in each individual sign. Cusa affirms in the *Compendium* that we distinguish one word from another only by the number and order of its letters², a principle applicable to the Tarocchi: the message of the allegories can only be deciphered by recognizing the order and hidden structure that articulates them as symbolic cryptography. The Cusan offers precise epistemological foundations for interpreting these allegories, their names and elements as a cryptographic system based on permutations, numbers, anagrams, and common phonetic roots. For Cusa, cognitive diversity is born from the number and order of signs, a conception perfectly coherent with the model identified in the Tarocchi: combinatorics as the generative matrix of knowledge.

The presence of ancient gods and classical mythologies in the Tarocchi responds to the Cusan search for a universal faith that integrates religious diversity. Unlike Gemistus Pletho, who advocated for a return to Hellenic paganism, Cusa considers that the peace of faith (*De pace fidei*, 1453) will be achieved through Christianity as a religion of love oriented toward unity. For this reason, in the Tarocchi the pagan visual forms are sustained upon a Christian foundation encoded throughout the entire set, as well as in some allegories that are plainly visible.

I previously indicated the finding of the name of Nicholas of Cusa ciphered in seven allegories without detailing the methodology employed. I now present more explicitly: the formal rule of extraction based on documented fifteenth-century techniques, the specific list of allegories implicated in the enciphered signature, and the deterministic result with exact probability. The unpublished work includes an extensive justification of these procedures with the corresponding visual apparatus. The present document offers a synthesis destined to establish the finding and promote its academic discussion.

¹ Nicholas of Cusa, *De ludo Globi*, II, 104

² See Nicholas of Cusa, *Compendium*, V, 15

2. METHODOLOGY AND EVIDENCE OF THE ENCIIPHERED SIGNATURE

2.1. Synopsis of the methodology for identifying the signature in the first four allegories:

1. *Identification of common phonetic root:* The root ME/MER present in four allegories linked to the principle of Mercury was identified: FAMEIO (E.2), MERCHADANTE (E.4), MELPOMENE (D.17), MERCVRIO (A.42). These allegories share four levels of concordances identified in this research as: visual, conceptual, crypto-onomastic, and analogical-cosmological concordances.
2. *Application of documented cryptographic technique:* Based on a method described in *De componendis cifris* (1467) by Leon Battista Alberti, the following extraction rule was applied: take from each inscription the letters immediately before and after the identified root.
3. *Exhaustive evaluation of combinations:* All possible combinations of 3, 4, 5, and 10 allegories among the 50 that compose the corpus were evaluated. No other combination produced a coherent proper name following this extraction method.
4. *Dual statistical validation:* The results were contrasted through two procedures implemented in Python: a) Monte Carlo simulation (500,000 repetitions). b) Deterministic proof (exhaustive enumeration of 230,300 combinations).

2.2. Allegories implicated in the enciphered signature

The sequence NICOLAC emerges only when combining four specific allegories linked to the cosmic principle of Mercury, whose phonetic root MER/ME is repeated in all of them:

Fig. 1. FAMEIO

Fig. 2. MERCHADANTE

Fig. 3. MELPOMEIE

Fig. 4. MERCVRIO

- FA(ME)IO — root ME, contributes “A” and “I”.
- (MER)CHADAITE — root MER, contributes “C”.
- (ME)LPO(ME)IE — double root ME, contributes “L”, “O”, and “I”.
- (MER)CVRIO — root MER, contributes “C”.

The only proper name in the fifteenth-century European context that can be formed by reordering these letters is NICOLAC. No other combination of allegories in the Tarocchi produces this result under the same extraction rule, as confirmed by the simulations and proofs conducted. This technique is described by Leon Battista Alberti in his work *De componendis cifris* (1467)³, and he indicates that persons holding high political and ecclesiastical offices employed similar methods of ciphering. The Cusan was recognized for his diplomatic abilities, occupying prominent positions as delegate and papal legate of different pontiffs: Eugene IV (1431–1447); Nicholas V (1447–1455); Callixtus III (1455–1458); and his great friend Pope Pius II (1458–1464), who was also close to Leon Battista Alberti.

The Monte Carlo simulations were equally applied to other names proposed as possible authors of the Tarocchi, evaluating various variants of Ludovico Lazzarelli, Basilio Bessarion, Leon Battista Alberti, Federico da Montefeltro, Andrea Mantegna, Francesco Squarcione, Lazzaro Bastiani, Baccio Baldini, and Parrasio Micheli. Even other ciphering techniques were applied considering graphic anomalies. In no case was success obtained.

2.3. Evidence that strengthens the finding

Additionally, of the 368 total letters present in the 50 allegory names of the Tarocchi, only two letters N appear inverted (И), both in these allegories linked to Mercury: MERCHADAITE (МЕРЧАДАИТЕ) and MELPOMEIE (МЕЛПОМЕИЕ).

Inverted characters or any unusual graphic sign constitute key elements in enciphered texts of the period, as Alberti indicates in *De componendis cifris*⁴. This inversion could signal precisely the beginning of the enciphered name, a datum especially significant if we consider that for Nicholas of Cusa in *De coniecturis*, the letter N is a symbolic figure of vital movement and of thought itself: its diagonal stroke links the vertical extremes, uniting beginning and end in a dynamic and symbolic continuity⁵.

The theme of the “children of the planets” was recurrent in literary and iconographic works of the fifteenth century, such as the engravings by Baccio Baldini, which represented under Mercury goldsmiths, writers, astronomers, scholars, clockmakers, and merchants, among other professions. However, in the Tarocchi two characters were specifically selected—FAMEIO and MERCHADANTE—who share the common phonetic root ME/MER in their

³ Leon Battista Alberti, “On Writing in Ciphers,” in *The Mathematical Works of Leon Battista Alberti*, ed. Kim Williams, Lionel March, and Stephen R. Wassell (Basel: Birkhäuser/Springer, 2010), 179.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 179-180

⁵ Nicholas of Cusa, *De coniecturis*, II 7, 109-110.

names, a selection that can hardly be attributed to chance given the availability of other mercurial professions that do not contain this root.

The fact that the name appears precisely around allegories linked with Mercury—a celestial body associated with philosophy, diplomacy, writing, communication, and service in the Platonic and Hermetic tradition—reinforces the hypothesis of authorial intentionality.

These four allegories reflect central aspects of the life of Nicholas of Cusa: ecclesiastical service, diplomatic activity, philosophy, and legal practice. The cardinal studied Canon Law at the University of Padua, training evident in the allegory of MERCHADANTE, whose clothing corresponds to that of a jurist and scholar of the fifteenth century, as documented by iconologist Claudia Cieri Via⁶ and other specialists. Moreover, the facial features of this figure show notable similarities with known portraits of Cusa:

Fig. 5

Fig. 2 (detail)

2.4. Statistical results:

- Only 1 exact combination of 4 allegories produces the name “NICOLAC”.
- The probability of this occurring by chance is 1 in 230,300 combinations (0.000433%).
- The Monte Carlo simulations replicate this result, confirming the extreme statistical rarity of the finding.

⁶ See Claudia Cieri Via, “I Tarocchi cosiddetti del «Mantegna»,” in *Le carte di corte: I tarocchi: Gioco e magia alla corte degli Estensi*, ed. Giordano Berti and Andrea Vitali (Bologna: Nuova Alfa Editoriale, 1987), 61.

2.5. Completing the enciphered signature (secondary-speculative hypothesis)

Through the application of extraction techniques documented in texts from the mid-fifteenth century, the name NICOLAC has been consistently obtained in the four allegories linked to Mercury. This is the only proper name formable in the Tarocchi set employing this specific methodology.

Alberti indicates that a single enciphered text can contain multiple techniques to conceal messages: “the combinations are practically infinite and, given the variants, the message will be highly ciphred.”⁷ That is to say that a single enciphered text can contain several simultaneous layers of concealment, which makes it practically indecipherable except to a reader with the complete key.

I do not consider that Cusa employed multiple layers of ciphering to “protect” information, but rather so that the student of these allegories would strive to observe, intuit, and understand this system of signs and symbols beyond the apparent, establishing multiple concordances and combinations among allegories. Based on this principle documented in both Alberti and Bacon, I have identified additional elements that could complete the signature obtained preliminarily. This interpretation, however, requires greater hermeneutic caution.

Just before the inverted N in MERCHADANTE the letters DA appear inserted in an unusual manner. In Venetian and other Italic languages of the fifteenth century, the usual term is *mercante* or *merchante*, without the particle DA. This anomaly could indicate the toponymic preposition DA, completing the name as NICOLA DA C.

These four mercurial allegories are connected by a visual and conceptual narrative with three others linked to the cosmic principle of Saturn:

- MISERO
- POLIMNIA
- SATVRNO

Both cosmic principles—Mercury and Saturn—can be related analogically and symbolically with the idea of origin or generative principle, a concept applicable to the toponym Cusa (Kues). Although in MERCVRIO the letter C immediately following the root MER was previously extracted, the connection with the Saturnine allegories suggests a change in the extraction dynamic. This multiplicity of techniques in a single text appears documented in both Bacon and Alberti, justified here by the symbolic link of both celestial bodies with the notion of origin or point of departure.

In this modified case, from MERCVRIO the first two letters following the root MER are taken (CV), and from SATVRNO we can take only the first two initials (SA) to form CVSA, or the first two initials and the final two (SA-NO). This extraction applied to both names symbolically linked to origin/place of origin produces CVSA/CVSANO, a toponym associated with the cardinal. Nevertheless, as we indicated before, these last techniques are speculative and require additional validation; they are not as solid as in the first case.

⁷ Alberti, “On Writing in Ciphers,” 179

3. CONCLUSION

The finding of the enciphered signature “NICOLAC” through extraction rules documented in the fifteenth century, with a probability of random occurrence of barely 0.000433% (1 in 230,300 combinations), constitutes significant evidence of cryptographic intentionality⁸. This result has been confirmed through 500,000 Monte Carlo simulations and exhaustive deterministic enumeration.

The specificity of the finding is reinforced by two crucial elements: first, the application of the same extraction technique to other names historically proposed as possible authors (Lazzarelli, Bessarion, Alberti, Mantegna, among others) did not produce any coherent result; second, NICOLAC is the only proper name formable in the complete set of 50 allegories under this specific methodology.

The convergence of multiple indicators—extreme statistical rarity, iconographic and biographical coherence (particularly in the allegory of MERCHADAITE), presence of graphic anomalies (inverted Ns with Cusan symbolism), and chronological concordance with the lost work *De figura mundi* (1462)—suggests the existence of a deliberate enciphered system. Additionally, considering the multiplicity of techniques documented in enciphered texts of the period, it is possible to complete the signature as NICOLA DA CVSA/CVSANO through narrative and visual connections with three allegories linked to Saturn, although this complementary analysis of a more speculative character requires additional validation.

This finding opens the possibility of attributing the intellectual authorship of the *Tarocchi de Figura Mundi* (known as Tarocchi del Mantegna) to the cardinal and philosopher Nicholas of Cusa or, subsidiarily, to members of his immediate intellectual circle. While it does not constitute direct documentary evidence, it represents a substantive advance that justifies reconsidering the nature of the Tarocchi: not merely as an artistic artifact, but as a philosophical-cryptographic system that anticipates the dynamic Cusan cosmos and is inscribed in the hermetic-combinatorial tradition of the Renaissance.

The identification of this enciphered signature establishes a methodological precedent for the study of other visual artifacts of the fifteenth century as possible carriers of enciphered messages, and underscores the necessity of interdisciplinary approaches that combine iconology, philosophy, historical cryptography, and statistical analysis in the investigation of Renaissance art.

Interdisciplinary relevance of the finding:

- ***Cusan studies:*** New attributable work that offers a didactic pathway for understanding key aspects of the philosophy, cosmology, and mystical theology of Nicholas of Cusa through a visual-combinatorial system.
- ***Iconology:*** Identification of visual cryptographic systems and attribution of authorship in a set of extensively studied engravings, opening new lines of iconographic interpretation.

⁸ Presented at the Geheimschriftenzoom, University of Wuppertal, October 24, 2025. Organizers: Jessika Nowak (Wuppertal), Paolo Bonavoglia (Venice), Camille Desenclos (Amiens), George Lasry (Tel Aviv), Klaus Schmeh (Gelsenkirchen), among other international specialists.

- **Historical cryptography:** Verifiable application of fifteenth-century techniques linking cryptanalysis, philosophy, and iconology in a visual artifact.
- **Renaissance studies:** Renewed understanding of the cultural context of the fifteenth century through a philosophical game that integrates Hermetic, Platonic, and combinatorial traditions.

The complete publication of this research in 2026 will present the integral philosophical-cryptographic system identified in the *Tarocchi de Figura Mundi*, including the complete network of anagrams, cosmological ruptures, and textual correspondences with Cusan work.

SOURCES OF IMAGES

Fig. 1. Master of the E-Series of the Tarocchi, *Fameio* (Servant), ca. 1465. Engraving with traces of gilding, 18.5 × 10.5 cm. National Gallery of Art, Washington D.C., Rosenwald Collection, 1943.3.9507. Series E, no. II. Public domain. Available at:

<https://www.nga.gov/artworks/12024-fameio-servant>

Fig. 2. Master of the E-Series of the Tarocchi, *The Merchant* (Merchadante), before 1467. Hand-colored engraving with gold. Cleveland Museum of Art, Dudley P. Allen Fund, 1924.432.4. Series E, no. IIII. Public domain. Available at:

<https://www.clevelandart.org/art/1924.432.4>

Fig. 3. Master of the E-Series of the Tarocchi, *Melpomene*, ca. 1465. Engraving with traces of gilding, 17.9 × 9.8 cm. National Gallery of Art, Washington D.C., Ailsa Mellon Bruce Fund, 1969.6.8. Series D, no. XVII. Public domain. Available at:

<https://www.nga.gov/artworks/51117-melpomene>

Fig. 4. Master of the E-Series of the Tarocchi, *Mercurio* (Mercury), ca. 1465. Engraving with gilding, 17.9 × 10 cm. National Gallery of Art, Washington D.C., Ailsa Mellon Bruce Fund, 1969.6.16. Series A, no. XXXXII. Public domain. Available at:

<https://www.nga.gov/artworks/51125-mercurio-mercury>

Fig. 5. Hartmann Schedel (1440-1514), portrait of Nicholas of Cusa with cardinal's galero, in *Liber Chronicarum* (Nuremberg Chronicle), Nuremberg, 1493. Woodcut. Public domain. Available at:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Cusanus_schedel_chronicle.jpg

BIBLIOGRAPHY CITED

Alberti, Leon Battista. "On Writing in Ciphers." In *The Mathematical Works of Leon Battista Alberti*, edited by Kim Williams, Lionel March, and Stephen R. Wassell, 176–200. Basel: Birkhäuser/Springer, 2010.

Bacon, Roger. *Fr. Rogeri Bacon Opera quædam hactenus inedita*. Vol. 1, *Opus Tertium, Opus Minus, Compendium Philosophicæ*. Edited by John Sherren Brewer. *Rerum Britannicarum Medii Ævi Scriptores*. London: Longman, Green, Longman, and Roberts, 1859. Reprint, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012.

Cieri Via, Claudia. "I Tarocchi cosiddetti del «Mantegna»." In *Le carte di corte: I tarocchi: Gioco e magia alla corte degli Estensi*, edited by Giordano Berti and Andrea Vitali, 49–77. Bologna: Nuova Alfa Editoriale, 1987.

Niccolò Cusano. *Opere filosofiche, teologiche e matematiche*. Edited by Enrico Peroli. Latin-Italian edition. Milan: Bompiani, 2017.

Note: The complete bibliography corresponding to the unpublished research will be published in the integral edition of the book.

KEYWORDS:

Nicholas of Cusa, Tarocchi del Mantegna, Tarocchi de Figura Mundi, cryptography, cryptanalysis, *ars combinatoria*, Renaissance, intellectual authorship, iconology, late medieval philosophy.